

A survey of researchers on rewarding data citation and reuse

Anton Boudreau Ninkov¹, Kathleen Gregory², Chantal Ripp³, Emma Roblin⁴, Isabella Peters⁵
and Stefanie Haustein⁶

¹ *anton.boudreau.ninkov@umontreal.ca*

Université de Montréal, École de bibliothéconomie et des sciences de l'information, Pavillon 3200 rue Jean-Brillant,
H3T 1N8, Montréal, Québec (Canada)

² *kathleen.gregory@uottawa.ca*

University of Ottawa, School of Information Studies, Scholarly Communications Lab, 55 Laurier Avenue East, K1N
6N5, Ottawa, Ontario (Canada)

University of Vienna, Faculty of Computer Science, Research Group Visualization and Data Analysis, Währinger
Straße 29/S6, Vienna (Austria)

³ *chantal.ripp@uottawa.ca*

University of Ottawa, School of Information Studies, Scholarly Communications Lab, 55 Laurier Avenue East, K1N
6N5, Ottawa, Ontario (Canada)

⁴ *eroblin@uottawa.ca*

University of Ottawa, School of Information Studies, Scholarly Communications Lab, 55 Laurier Avenue East, K1N
6N5, Ottawa, Ontario (Canada)

⁵ *i.peters@zbw.eu*

ZBW Leibniz Information Center for Economics & Kiel University, Duesternbrooker Weg 120, 24015 Kiel
(Germany)

⁶ *stefanie.haustein@uottawa.ca*

University of Ottawa, School of Information Studies, Scholarly Communications Lab, 55 Laurier Avenue East, K1N
6N5, Ottawa, Ontario (Canada)

Observatoire des Sciences et des Technologies (OST), Centre
Interuniversitaire de Recherche sur la Science et la Technologie (CIRST), Université du Québec à Montréal, CP
8888, Succ. Centre-Ville, H3C 3P8, Montréal, Québec (Canada)

Abstract

This research-in-progress paper presents results from the largest known survey (n=2,492) to explicitly investigate data citation and reuse practices among a representative sample of academic authors across academic disciplines. This analysis focuses on participants' preferences and attitudes towards rewarding their own data work and that by others. The results indicate that assessing the reach and influence of data is important or extremely important for researchers across disciplines. However, there are significant disciplinary differences identified in preferences for recognition and reward of practices regarding research data management, sharing, citation, reuse and assessment. For example, we observe that assessing the reach and influence of both their own and the data of others, as well as getting credit for reusing data, is more important to researchers in Medical and Health Sciences and Agricultural Sciences than other groups. Additionally, researchers from Social Science found it more important to trace a variety of metrics and information about their own data compared to most other disciplines.

Introduction

Although data is essential to research and discovery, and, through efforts by the open science community (Wilkinson et al., 2016), have gained some importance in the scholarly communication process, the scientific reward system has not yet caught up with valuing data as a research output (Pierce et al., 2019). Even if funding agencies increasingly require data sharing and detailed

research data management plans (Briney et al., 2017; Nelson, 2022 (OSTP memorandum)), data collection, cleaning and curation are not yet considered valuable contributions to scientific advancement. Besides discussions about the role of research data for the reproducibility of studies and the efficiency of science (Munafò et al., 2017; Borgman, 2015), reuse of data is not typically considered ‘original research’ in some disciplines and is disincentivized (Longo & Drazen, 2016). The scientific reward system lags behind in recognizing open data practices (Alperin et al., 2020). However, improving the practices of researchers to acknowledge their data reuse through appropriate means (i.e., formal citations of data) has been shown to be a driver of data sharing (Tenopir et al., 2011, 2020). Data metrics that capture views, downloads and reuse of datasets have been identified as potential indicators to assess the value of data, incentivize its sharing and raise its status to first-class scholarly output (Lowenberg et al., 2019). As for scholarly articles, data metrics can support the assessment of relevance and quality of research data that may be reused by third parties (Weber, 2021) and for self-assessment (NISO, 2016). However, as with the motivation and rewards for making data open and easily shareable (Borgman, 2015), there is reason to believe that there are different notions of what constitutes data, its usefulness, and its impact across scholarly disciplines.

Methods

This paper analyzes a subsection of a survey on data citation and reuse practices (Gregory et al., 2022a), which focuses on participants’ preferences and attitudes towards recognizing and rewarding data work. Based on a random sample of corresponding authors of journal articles indexed in the Web of Science stratified by academic discipline, the survey was completed by 2,492 participants, representing a response rate of 1.6%. The recruitment and sampling methodology are described in further detail in Gregory et al. (2022b).

Each respondent of the survey was asked to complete a questionnaire consisting of up to 33 questions (Gregory et al., 2022a). The questionnaire included several different types of questions, including binary, multiple choice, 5-point Likert scale, multiple response, and open-ended. We asked all respondents questions regarding the following three aspects related to recognizing and rewarding data work across disciplines:

1. Recognition and reward of research data production and documentation.
2. Recognition and reward of data sharing and reuse.
3. Assessment of quality, reach and influence of data.

We asked questions about the importance of possible data metrics for data which all respondents (may) reuse and share. We analysed the data to see if there were statistically significant differences in terms of how researchers from different disciplines (i.e., OECD Fields of Science and Technology Classification major fields Natural sciences, Engineering and technology, Medical and health sciences, Agricultural sciences, Social sciences, Humanities) viewed the importance of rewarding data work. Differences were calculated by using Kruskal–Wallis tests for significance, which ranks all the responses 1 - 2492 (or the number of responses to that question) and measures the difference in the mean rank between each discipline. We used descriptive statistics and visualizations to get a better sense of how researchers responded to the questions.

In Table 1, we present all the questions from the survey about rewarding data work and their results by discipline. We have indicated in the table which questions had significant differences observed between the disciplines and have coloured each cell of the table to reflect the difference between the results of each discipline and the average result. In the table, blue means that the result of that discipline is greater than the average (i.e., they responded that it is more important than the

average) and red means less than the average (i.e., they responded that it is less important than the average). The density of the colouring reflects how much greater than the average the result was (i.e., if the colouring is denser, then that means the result is further away from the average).

Findings

Across disciplines, assessing the reach and influence of data is important or extremely important for researchers, particularly for their own data (70.6% of researchers) but also when assessing data which they may reuse (54.9% of researchers). Comparing answers between disciplines, Medical and Health Sciences and Agricultural Sciences researchers find it significantly more important to assess the reach and influence of both their data and others' data than researchers in the Humanities and Social Sciences.

Various types of metrics and information can assist researchers in the assessment and evaluation of data. When selecting data for reuse, 62.3% of researchers across disciplines find it important or extremely important to have descriptions or narratives about how data have been used. Approximately half of all researchers indicated that it is important or extremely important to know the number of citations which data have accrued (50.7% of researchers) and to have information about the context in which data had already been used, e.g., in which country or at which institution (48.1% of researchers). We found significant differences in how researchers from different disciplines answered this question. Agricultural Science researchers in particular find it more important to know the number of times data have been downloaded, viewed, if data have been used outside of the scholarly system, and where the data have been used.

Across disciplines, 82% of researchers find it important or extremely important to know the number of citations which their data have received. This is approximately 30% greater than the percentage of researchers who find citations to be important in evaluating others' data for reuse. The majority of researchers (69.8% of researchers) indicated that descriptions or narratives describing how their own data have been reused would be important or extremely important. Significant disciplinary differences were identified, as displayed in Table 1. For example, researchers in the Medical and Health Sciences found it more important to have information about the number of traditionally proposed data metrics (i.e., the most data citations, downloads, and views). The number of times data have been viewed was also important in the Humanities. However, having a data narrative describing both other people's data and their own data was less important in the Humanities than in other disciplines. Social scientists found it more important than other disciplines to have information about who has used their data and if their data has received recognition outside the scholarly system.

Compared to other disciplinary groups, Social Sciences and Humanities researchers do not rely as much on traditional metrics (e.g., the number of data citations or views) when assessing data for reuse. Social scientists found it more important to trace a variety of metrics and information about their own data compared to Humanities scholars, who found it less important to track data citations to their own data or in having detailed descriptions describing how their data were used. Interestingly, Humanities researchers also found it less important than other disciplinary groups to have a narrative describing how data are used, both when assessing others' data and when tracing their own data. It could be that a Humanities publication already provides the context that a data narrative could provide.

Table 1. Views on rewarding data citation and reuse by discipline (comparison of mean rank).

Question (* indicates questions that had significant differences between disciplines (p<0.05))	Nat. Sci.	Eng. & Tech.	Med. & Health Sci.	Agr. Sci.	Soc. Sci.	Hum.
How important is it to you to:						
*assess the reach and influence of your own data? (n = 2426)	1198.74	1190.18	1327.98	1331.41	1130.38	1134.67
get credit specifically for sharing your own data? (n = 2418)	1223.76	1168.91	1258.05	1206.38	1183.40	1071.48
*assess the reach and influence of other people's data which you reuse? (n = 2382)	1186.67	1212.27	1267.99	1252.45	1113.22	1092.57
*get credit for reusing other people's data? (n = 2352)	1171.11	1188.94	1234.7	1315.65	1119.57	1015.52
How important would it be for you to know the following information about your data (n = 2492):						
the number of citations the data have received?	1209.8	1254.84	1323.87	1231.5	1253.8	1202.87
*the number of times the data have been downloaded?	1176.04	1208.67	1333.13	1319.33	1312.95	1290.42
*the number of times the data have been viewed?	1183.29	1207.42	1368.26	1308.89	1255.31	1327.55
*information about where the data were used?	1146.23	1213.67	1358.29	1363.35	1346.01	1258.82
*descriptions or a narrative providing details about how the data were used?	1221.99	1196.44	1308.83	1257.64	1287.23	1153.3
*information about who has used the data?	1158.12	1171.17	1357.07	1253.29	1381.29	1229.46
*if the data have received recognition outside the scholarly system?	1189.45	1164.42	1305.72	1255.54	1363.46	1260.56
How important would it be for you to know the following information about others' data which you may reuse (n = 2492):						
*the number of citations the data have received	1197.57	1410.07	1324.55	1415.45	1139.66	1158.28
*the number of times the data have been downloaded?	1182.13	1349.49	1315.32	1507.34	1201.66	1172.77
*the number of times the data have been viewed?	1194.75	1328.19	1350.18	1452.4	1146.19	1259.24
*information about where the data were used?	1142.86	1268.98	1362.83	1517.5	1274.75	1259.47
descriptions or a narrative providing details about how the data were used?	1226.16	1225.21	1290.7	1294.46	1280.61	1095.56
*information about who has used the data?	1182.78	1227.19	1331.30	1351.93	1283.43	1272.72
*if the data have received recognition outside the scholarly system?	1175.35	1290.33	1318.02	1375.25	1258.33	1302.64

We also observe that assessing the reach and influence of both their own and the data of others, as well as getting credit for reusing data, is more important to researchers in Medical and Health Sciences and Agricultural Sciences than other groups. Researchers in these disciplines want to know a variety of information about others' data before they reuse them, including the number of data downloads, views, and information about where and how data have been used. Metrics such as data downloads naturally imply that the data in question can be downloaded; such metrics may be less relevant for researchers who interact with data in a way that does not require a download (i.e., in fields within the Natural Sciences such as climate/atmospheric sciences). Medical and Health researchers also want to know the number of citations their data have received more than other disciplines, perhaps reflecting increasing data citation advocacy efforts within the Medical and Health community.

Discussion

This research-in-progress-paper presents the first results (in relation to rewarding data work) of a survey across a representative sample of researchers. It provides evidence for disciplinary differences in preferences for recognition and reward of practices regarding research data management, sharing, citation, reuse, and assessment.

The descriptive and statistical analyses presented in this research-in-progress paper have revealed insights into the research questions already. In this paper, we have presented an analysis of only one section of the survey questionnaire. Future work will examine other aspects of data citation and reuse practices. Additionally, upcoming research includes analyses focusing on differences between career stage and gender, as well as conducting semi-structured interviews with researchers that do reuse data and those who do not.

Acknowledgements

The Alfred P. Sloan Foundation (Sloan Grant G-2020-12670) supported this work.

References

- Alperin, J. P., Schimanski, L. A., La, M., Niles, M. T., & McKiernan, E. C. (2020). The value of data and other non-traditional scholarly outputs in academic review, promotion, and tenure in Canada and the United States. In A. Berez-Kroeker, B. McDonnell, E. Koller, & L. Collister, *Open Handbook of Linguistic Data Management*. MIT Press. <http://doi.org/10.17613/ye06-n045>
- Borgman, C. L. (2015). *Big data, little data, no data: Scholarship in the networked world*. The MIT Press. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/9963.001.0001>
- Briney, K., Goben, A., & Zilinski, L. (2017). Institutional, Funder, and Journal Data Policies. In L. Johnston, *Curating Research Data, Volume One: Practical Strategies for Your Digital Repository*. ACRL. https://dc.uwm.edu/lib_staffart/8/
- Gregory, K., Ninkov, A., Peters, I., & Haustein, S. (2022a). Questionnaire: A survey on data citation and reuse practices. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6505207>
- Gregory, K., Ninkov, A., Ripp, C., Peters, I., & Haustein, S. (2022b). Surveying practices of data citation and reuse across disciplines. *Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators*. International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators, Granada, Spain. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6951437>
- Longo, D. L., & Drazen, J. M. (2016). Data sharing. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 374(3), 276-277.
- Lowenberg, D., Chodacki, J., Fenner, M., Kemp, J., & Jones, M. B. (2019). *Open Data Metrics: Lighting the Fire*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3525349>

- Munafò, M. R., Nosek, B. A., Bishop, D. V., Button, K. S., Chambers, C. D., Percie du Sert, N., ... & Ioannidis, J. (2017). A manifesto for reproducible science. *Nature human behaviour*, *1*(1), 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-016-0021>
- National Information Standards Organization (NISO). (2016). NISO RP-25-2016, outputs of the NISO alternative assessment project [output report]. NISO. p. 86. Retrieved from <https://www.niso.org/publications/rp-25-2016-altmetrics>
- Nelson, A. (2022). Ensuring Free, Immediate, and Equitable Access to Federally Funded Research. <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/08-2022-OSTP-Public-Access-Memo.pdf>. Accessed: 2022-11-24
- Pierce, H. H., Dev, A., Statham, E., & Bierer, B. E. (2019). Credit data generators for data reuse. *Nature*, *570*(7759), 30–32. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-019-01715-4>
- Tenopir, C., Allard, S., Douglass, K., Aydinoglu, A. U., Wu, L., Read, E., Manoff, M., & Frame, M. (2011). Data Sharing by Scientists: Practices and Perceptions. *PLoS ONE*, *6*(6), e21101. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0021101>
- Tenopir, C., Rice, N. M., Allard, S., Baird, L., Borycz, J., Christian, L., Grant, B., Olendorf, R., & Sandusky, R. J. (2020). Data sharing, management, use, and reuse: Practices and perceptions of scientists worldwide. *PLOS ONE*, *15*(3), e0229003. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0229003>
- Weber, T. (2021). *Machine-actionable assessment of research data products* (Doctoral dissertation, lmu). <https://doi.org/10.5282/edoc.28346>
- Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, Ij. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers, R., ... Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, *3*(1), 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>